

A study to evaluate the effectiveness of snake and ladder game on knowledge of personal hygiene among primary school children in Gamei U.G.U.P school, BBSR.

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Abstract: Background: Cleanliness is one of the most important cleaning habits for human being in order to live a healthy and happy life. It is a best quality everyone needs to have or develop with time. Following cleanliness helps us in keeping our body and mind very energetic, active, fresh and healthy. It keeps us away from the diseases as it is the part of healthy civilization. If we follow this habit all through our life regularly we will always be free from infectious diseases.¹

Methodology: Quantitative approach with quasi experimental research design was adopted. Total 40 primary school children were selected for the study using stratified random sampling technique. Subjects were randomly assigned into the primary school children (n=40). Snake and Ladder game was given to the group. The game includes discussion, questioning, group activity. The tools used to collect the data were as follows: (1) Demographic questionnaire (2) A structured interview schedule on personal hygiene which consisted of 24 questions. Baseline assessment was done on the 1st day, then pre-test was done & the Snake and Ladder game was done the same day. The game includes of discussion, questioning, group activity, role play etc. given for seven days followed by post-test was done in the group. The data analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics with SPSS 21 version.

Result: The mean post-test score 18.6 (SD=1.23) was more than the pre-test mean score 9.15(SD= 3.97). Before the game, 0 students had adequate knowledge, 11 (27.5%) students had moderately adequate knowledge and 29 (72.5%) students had inadequate knowledge. After game the level of knowledge increased significantly and 33(82.5%) students gained adequate knowledge, 7(17.5%) students had gained moderately adequate level of knowledge, and only 0 students had inadequate level of knowledge. It was a significant increase in the level of knowledge regarding personal hygiene among the primary school children after the snake and ladder game. $t=23.6$ ($P>0.001$). Majority of the background factors such as age, sex, father's education, mother's education and number of siblings, were associated with the post-test score.

It was inferred that there was a significant increase in the level of knowledge among the primary school children after the snake and ladder game.

Conclusion: Thus, the game regarding snake and ladder game was effective in improving level of knowledge regarding personal hygiene among primary school children.

Keywords: Personal hygiene, primary school children, snake and ladder game

Introduction

“Children are natural Zen masters; their world is brand new in each and every moment.” - John Bradshaw

“Every child is born a naturalist. His eyes are by nature, open to the glories of the stars, beauty of the flowers and the mystery of life.”- R.search.

V Curtis, W Schmidt et al, (2011) The term “hygiene” is derived from Hygeia, the Greek goddess of health, cleanliness and sanitation. Hygiene is also the name of a branch of science that deals with the promotion and preservation of health, also called hygienic.²

Hygiene is a set of practices performed to preserve health. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), "Hygiene refers to conditions and practices that help to maintain health and prevent the spread of diseases." Personal hygiene refers to maintaining the body's cleanliness.

VS Smith et al, (2008) Personal hygiene is an important aspect for children of primary school age. Teaching them basic precautions can help in preventing the spread of infections. School health services play a major role in the control of infections. Teachers and health visitors should impart education to avoid the spread of infection.³

EL Larson et al, (2007) Hygiene is a position of practices performed for the protection of health. According to WHO hygiene refers the circumstances and practices that help to encourage, sustain health and prevent the spread of diseases. According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention stated that prevention of spread of germs in the schools is essential to the health of youth, schools and state. It also helps to give a good first impression and good feelings to others. The school Health Program includes all school health services, school health environment, school health education, and school nutrition programs.⁴

UNICEF data obtained by the 2004 census of India, through which, for the first time, a direct statistical estimation of prevalence of hygiene was adopted that indicated the presence of 21.9 million unhygienic practices (2.13% of total population). Environmental sanitation and hygienic programme was stated as a vertical programme with the objective of promoting hygienic and environmental sanitation. Establishing such an uni-purpose health programme for school children are justifiable, at the end of the year 2003, 45% of the school children with unhygienic practices were in India. Nearly 0.5 million children affected by disease due to improper hygienic and poor sanitation.⁵

A Vipin et al, (2014) Snake and ladder game is well versed, vibrant, active and popular board game in India. This game is associated with local custom and cultural practices and the knowledge of playing this game is been imparted through generations. Snake and ladder game always has the excitement, thrill, exhilaration for children while playing as a group. This game has been used in health programs in many developing countries and adapted to teach the children in an innovative way. This study uses a systematically organized board game on personal hygiene (hair, eyes, nose, mouth, ears, skin, hands, nails and genitalia) constructed by the investigator.⁶

Objectives: The main objective of the study was to assess the effect of snake and ladder game on knowledge of personal hygiene among primary school children.

Methods & materials

Quantitative approach with pre experimental one group pre-test and post-test research design was adopted to test the effect of snake and ladder game on level of knowledge of personal hygiene among primary school children. The present study was carried out in the Gamei U.G.U.P School, Bhubaneswar, Odisha. Primary school children having age between 8 to 10 years, present on the day of data collection, are willing to participate were included in the study. Children are not willing to participate, not available during data collection were excluded from the study. Total 40 primary school children were selected for the study by using systematic random sampling technique. Subjects were randomly assigned to the group (n=40). Before conducting study, ethical permission was taken from the Institutional Ethical Committee (IEC). The tools used to collect the data were as follows: (1) Demographic questionnaire (2) Self structured interview questions on personal hygiene. Reliability of the structured interview schedule was done through test- retest method among 10 samples. Reliability was computed using Karl Pearson's Correlation Coefficient Method. The reliability was found to be $r=0.97$. Pre-test is done before the group gets intervention so the pre-test can represent the group's initial ability. The intervention here is the application of media to the group. Post-test was conducted after the group received intervention. The data analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics with SPSS 21 version. The study period was from March 2018 to September 2018.

Result

Table-1: Demographic data in terms of age, gender, religion, types of family, mother education, mother occupation, number of siblings, birth order of child

Characteristics	Group	
	F	%
Age in years		
8- 9	20	50
9- 10	20	50
Gender		
Male	16	53
Female	14	47
Religion		
Hindu	25	62.5
Muslim	8	20
Christianity	5	12.5
Others	2	5
Types of Family		
Nucler	19	47.5
Joint	21	52.5
Other	Nil	-
Mother Education		
Primary	Nil	-
High school	11	27.5
Higher secondary school	8	20
Diploma degree	21	52.5
Mother Occupation		
House wife	29	72.5
Employed	11	27.5

Number of siblings		
One	10	25
Two	20	50
More than two	10	25
Birth order of child		
First	10	25
Second	15	37.5
Third or More	15	37.5

The above Table-1 revealed that in group, Equal numbers 20 (50%) were in the age group of 8-9 & 9-10 years. Equal number 20 (50%) of the primary school children, were males & females. Majority, 25 (62.5%) were Hindus. Among the primary school children, majority 21 (52.5%) were from joint family. Majority 21 (52.5%) had finished Diploma/degree. Majority 16 (40%) had finished high school. Majority 29 (72.5%) had House wife. Majority 20(50%) had Two Child. Majority 15(37.5%) had second and third.

Table-2: Data on the level of knowledge among primary school children before and after the snake and ladder game

Level of Knowledge	Mean	Range(H-L)	SD
Pretest	9.15	17-4	3.97
Posttest	18.6	21-16	1.23

Table-2 shows the post-test mean score 18.6 (SD=1.23) was more than the pre-test mean score 9.15(SD= 3.97).It was inferred that level of knowledge regarding personal hygiene among primary school children had significantly increased after the snake and ladder game.

Table-3: Level of knowledge among primary school children in group.

n= 40

Level of knowledge	Group			
	Pre-test		Post-test	
	f	%	f	%
<50% (inadequate knowledge)	29	72.5	Nil	-
50- 75% (moderately adequate knowledge)	11	27.5	7	17.5
>75% (adequate knowledge)	Nil	-	33	82.5

Table- 3 shows the comparison of level of knowledge among primary school children before and after the snake and ladder game. Before the game 29 (72.5%) students had inadequate knowledge. After the game the level of knowledge increased significantly and 33(82.5%) students gained adequate knowledge. This shows the snake and ladder game was effective among the primary school children.

Table-4: Effectiveness of snake and ladder game

N=40

Level of knowledge	Mean	SD	t test	df	P value
Pre-test	9.15	3.97	23.6	39	0.0001*
Post-test	18.6	1.23		39	

Table-4 shows there was a significant increase in the level of knowledge regarding personal hygiene among the primary school children after the snake and ladder game. $t=23.6$ ($P>0.001$). Chi square test was computed to find the association between the level of knowledge & selected socio demographic variables. There was a significant association found between the religion (chi square= 18.28, $P= 0.043$).

It was inferred that there was a significant association between the post-test score on the level of knowledge regarding personal hygiene and background factors among primary school children. Snake and ladder game was independently effective to improve the level of knowledge regarding personal hygiene.

Discussion

Pre- test mean level of knowledge regarding personal hygiene among the primary school was 9.15(S.D=3.97). Majority, 29 (72.5%) of the primary school children had inadequate level of knowledge regarding personal hygiene before the snake and ladder game. Oyibo PG found that although a number of the children had adequate knowledge related to basic personal hygiene their practice related to same was poor.⁷ Deepak Kumar. J. et.al said that school going children had inadequate knowledge of hand hygiene.⁸

There was a significant increase in the level of knowledge regarding personal hygiene among the primary school children after the snake and ladder game. $t=23.6$ ($P>0.0001$)

The post-test mean level of knowledge regarding personal hygiene among the primary school children was 18.6 (S.D=1.23). 33(82.5%) students gained adequate knowledge, 7 (17.5%) students had gained moderately adequate level of knowledge, and no students had inadequate level of knowledge after the snake and ladder game.

Lakshmi Prasanthi K.reported that the game was an effective method of imparting information on common ailments to the children.⁹

There was a significant association between the pre-test score on the level of knowledge regarding personal hygiene and background factors such as age, sex, father's education, mother's education & no. of siblings, were associated with the post-test score whereas sex, religion, type of family, mothers occupation, & birth order of the child were not significant among primary school children. ($P>0.05$) The highest χ^2 value was found to be: $\chi^2=18.28$. Dr.Nazar Ali.Sheren et al reported that age was a significant factor for the students' responses about knowledge of personal hygiene and knowledge of infectious disease.¹⁰

Chythra Rao & Raghavendra Rao (2012) found that education for teachers and parents on maintenance of sound personal hygiene and a clean environment is important.¹¹

Limitation of the study: The limitation of the study was, Study had no control group. It includes small sample size and the time period of data collection was limited.

Conclusion

The study revealed that the snake and ladder game effective in improving the level of knowledge of the primary school children. This study assessed the educational game based learning media in the form of Snake and ladder. The use of fun learning media is expected to motivate students to learn. Based on the results, there are improvements on the students learning outcomes.

Ethical clearance: Obtained

Source of funding: None

Conflict of interest: None

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